

Comparative analysis of keratinophilic fungi from the soils of Khardung and Khardung La (Ladakh), India

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ABSTRACT

The present research work was undertaken to study the diversity of keratinophilic fungi from the unexplored soils of Khardung and Khardung La (Ladakh). This was done with a view to evaluate the relationship between the keratinophilic fungi and the keratinous material present in the soil. The soil samples examined from Khardung La were found to be 80% positive for keratinophilic fungi, whereas that of Khardung were 100% positive. A total of 29 keratinophilic species belonging to 13 genera were recovered by keratin bait technique from the soils of Khardung. However, from Khardung La, only 7 species belonging to 3 genera were recovered. The recovered myco-keratinophiles consisted of 5 species each of *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium*, 4 species of *Chrysosporium*, 3 species of *Paecilomyces*, 2 species each of *Acremonium*, *Gliocladium* and *Penicillium* and 1 species each of *Beauveria*, *Cladosporium*, *Embellisia*, *Emericella*, *Epicoccum*, and *Sagenomella*. Comparison of diversity indices showed a significant difference in species richness between the two sites i.e., Khardung (29) and Khardung La (7). The values of Shannon's diversity index and Simpson's diversity index were 3.27 and 0.96 respectively for Khardung, whereas these values were 1.88 and 0.84 respectively for Khardung La. Sorenson's similarity index showed a value of 38.89% for these two sites, which indicates that some of the species present in Khardung La soils are also prevalent in Khardung soils.

Key words: Keratinophilic fungi, keratin, Khardung, Khardung la, Ladakh, soil.

INTRODUCTION

Keratinophilic fungi are attracting lot of attention throughout the world because they play an important role in the decomposition of keratin substrates and could be used in bioremediation of such wastes and waste-contaminated sites. Secondly, some keratinophilic fungi are potentially pathogenic to animals, including human beings and therefore, studies on these fungi in a particular environment is of hygienic and epidemiological importance [1, 2]. In nature, the keratinophiles exist as self-sufficient

saprophytes as long as environmental conditions are favourable but they may become parasitic by accident and then ultimately pathogenic. Soils rich in keratinous material are found to be most conducive for the growth and occurrence of keratinophilic fungi, which act as a potential source of infection for human beings and other animals [3, 4].

In India, a number of reports have appeared concerning the distribution of keratinophilic fungi from various habitats [5-16]. In our state of Jammu and Kashmir, only few soils have been investigated for this group of fungi [8, 9, 12, 13].

Therefore, present research work was undertaken to isolate and characterise keratinophilic fungi from the soils of Khardung and Khardung La situated in the Ladakh region of Jammu and Kashmir. Ladakh is one of the most elevated and least inhabited region of the world, located between 32° 15' - 36° N latitude and 75° 15' - 80° 15' E longitude, which falls in the high altitude regions of Great Central Himalayas. Cold desert-like conditions prevail throughout the year; precipitation is scanty with less than 70 mm annually, which mostly occurs in the form of snow. The soils are coarse, sandy in texture, poor in organic matter and alkaline in reaction. Khardung La (La in Tibetan means pass) is the highest mountain pass of India (17,582 feet above sea level), which lies North of Leh and is the gateway to Shyok and Nubra valley, whereas Khardung is a sparsely populated village of Nubra valley, the most beautiful valley of Ladakh, whose height above sea-level is 14,738 feet. These are geographically diverse regions and the cold climate makes them potentially interesting areas to study the distribution of keratinophilic fungi as these areas provide an unusual natural environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling was done by collecting the soil from different sites of Khardung and Khardung La in pre-sterilised polythene bags by using sterilised spatula. Samples were brought to the laboratory and keratin-bait technique of Vanbreuseghem [17] was used to isolate keratinophilic fungi. For this purpose, sterilised petridishes were half-filled with soil samples, moistened with 10-15 ml of sterilised distilled water and baited with different pre-sterilised keratinic baits like human hair, nails, bird feathers and sheep wool. These petridishes were incubated at 28±2°C for the growth of keratinophilic fungi. Fungal growth occurring on different baits was isolated, purified and maintained on Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA) medium supplemented with chloramphenicol (0.05mg/ml) and cycloheximide (0.5mg/l). The keratinophilic fungal isolates were identified on the basis of their cultural and morphological details by following different standard keys [18, 19] along

with other standard mycological manuals [20-22]. Distribution, percentage frequency of occurrence and relative abundance were calculated as given below:

Distribution (%) = No. of isolates of a fungus / Total no. of isolates X 100.

Frequency of occurrence (%) = No. of positive samples / Total no. of samples X 100.

To compare the diversity of keratinophilic fungi from the two sites, data was analysed statistically using Shannon and Wiener's diversity index [H=

$-\sum_{i=1}^s (pi \ln pi)$] and Simpson's diversity index (1-D). Here D is Simpson's dominance, [D = $\sum_{i=1}^s (pi)^2$] and pi is relative frequency [23, 24].

Similarity between the two sites was assessed by using Sorensen's similarity index, which is equal to $2C / S_1 + S_2$, here S_1 = species present in site 1, S_2 = species present in site 2 and C = species "common" to both sites [25]. Richness of the sites was assessed as the total number of species present in all the sampling units of a site.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the period of investigation, all the soil samples collected from Khardung were found to be 100% positive for these fungi indicating, thereby, that Khardung soils are favourable for the growth, development and diffusion of keratinophilic fungi (Table 1). However, from Khardung La, only 80% soil samples were positive for keratinophilic fungi (Table 1). This observation can be correlated with the higher altitude, thick snow cover, very cold and harsh climatic conditions and less activity of humans and animals, which allow low keratin content in the soil of Khardung La. All these factors, therefore create conditions, which are not very favourable for the growth, development and diffusion of keratinophilic fungi at Khardung La.

A total of 29 keratinophilic fungal species belonging to 13 genera were isolated from the

soils of Khardung whereas only 7 species belonging to 3 genera were recovered from the soils of Khardung La by keratin-bait technique (Table 1). From the data obtained, it was observed that the keratinophilic fungal species recovered from Khardung La soils were present in Khardung soils also.

However, in Khardung soils, frequency occurrence of recovered keratinophilic species was higher than that obtained in Khardung La soils.

Out of the 29 keratinophilic fungal species recovered from the soils of Khardung,

Table 1: Comparative analysis of keratinophilic fungi recovered from the soil of Khardung and Khardung La

Fungal species recovered	Khardung soil Altitude: 14,738 feet above sea level; pH: 8.9 Number of soil samples examined 'n'=12			Khardung La soil Altitude: 17,582 feet above sea level; pH: 8.4 Number of soil samples examined 'n'=10		
	No. of positive soil samples	Distribution %	Frequency %	No. of positive soil samples	Distribution %	Frequency %
<i>Acremonium bacilliforme</i>	2	2.2	16.7	-	-	-
<i>A. implicatum</i>	4	4.3	33.3	-	-	-
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i>	6	6.5	50.0	3	17.6	30.0
<i>A. parasiticus</i>	2	2.2	16.7	-	-	-
<i>A. sydowii</i>	4	4.3	33.3	2	11.8	20.0
<i>A. ustus</i>	3	3.3	25.0	2	11.8	20.0
<i>A. wentii</i>	2	2.2	16.7	-	-	-
<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	6	6.5	50.0	4	23.5	40.0
<i>Chrysosporium inops</i>	2	2.2	16.7	-	-	-
<i>C. merdarium</i>	5	5.4	41.7	-	-	-
<i>C. queenslandicum</i>	5	5.4	41.7	-	-	-
<i>Chrysosporium anamorph of Gymnoascus demonbreunii</i>	2	2.2	16.7	-	-	-
<i>Cladosporium cladosporioides</i>	3	3.3	25.0	-	-	-
<i>Embellisia chlamydospora</i>	2	2.2	16.7	-	-	-
<i>Emericella variegata</i>	3	3.3	25.0	-	-	-
<i>Epicoccum nigrum</i>	1	1.1	8.3	-	-	-
<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	4	4.3	33.3	3	17.6	30.0
<i>F. sporotrichioides</i>	4	4.3	33.3	2	11.8	20.0
<i>F. trichothecioides</i>	1	1.1	8.3	-	-	-
<i>F. semitectum</i>	3	3.3	25.0	-	-	-
<i>F. moniliforme</i> var. <i>subglutinans</i>	2	2.2	16.7	1	5.9	10.0
<i>Gliocladium catenulatum</i>	2	2.2	16.7	-	-	-
<i>G. roseum</i>	4	4.3	33.3	-	-	-
<i>Paecilomyces lilacinus</i>	5	5.4	41.7	-	-	-
<i>P. marquandii</i>	4	4.3	33.3	-	-	-
<i>P. variotii</i>	4	4.3	33.3	-	-	-
<i>Penicillium brevicompactum</i>	3	3.3	25.0	-	-	-
<i>P. griseofulvum</i>	2	2.2	16.7	-	-	-
<i>Sagenomella alba</i>	2	2.2	16.7	-	-	-

'-' indicates absence of fungal species

Aspergillus flavus and *Beauveria bassiana* were the most dominant species, each showing 50% frequency occurrence, whereas from Khardung La soils, *B. bassiana* was dominant with 40% frequency occurrence and *A. flavus* showed 30% frequency. Both these species formed the bulk of the recovered keratinophilic fungal species. They are also considered as potential pathogenic fungi [31] and have been reported as keratinophilic by other researchers also [16, 28-30]. Comparison of other keratinophiles recovered from the two sites showed that frequency occurrence of *Fusarium oxysporum*, *F. sporotrichioides*, *F. moniliforme* var. *subglutinans*, *Aspergillus sydowii* and *A. ustus* from Khardung soils was 33.3%, 33.3%, 16.7%, 33.3% and 25% respectively, whereas from Khardung La soils their frequency occurrence was detected to be 30.0%, 20.0%, 10.0%, 20.0% and 20.0% respectively. This shows that the values of frequency occurrence of the recovered keratinophilic fungi from Khardung La were lesser than that observed in Khardung soils. This indicates that freezing temperature throughout the year along with low keratinous material present in the soils of Khardung La restricts the growth and development of keratinophiles. All these species have been reported earlier as keratinophilic by many researchers [9,16,28,29,32-34].

Keratinophilic fungal species isolated from Khardung soils also included *Chrysosporium merdarium*, *C. queenslandicum* and *Paecilomyces lilacinus*, each with 41.7% occurrence; *Acremonium implicatum*, *Gliocladium roseum* and *Paecilomyces marquandii*, each having 33.3% frequency; *Cladosporium cladosporioides*, *Emericella variicolor*, *Fusarium semitectum* and *Penicillium brevicompactum*, each with 25% frequency occurrence; *Acremonium bacillisporum*, *Aspergillus parasiticus*, *A. wentii*, *Chrysosporium anamorph* of *Gymnoascus demonbreunii*, *Chrysosporium inops*, *Embellisia chlamydospora*, *Gliocladium catenulatum*, *Penicillium griseofulvum* and *Sagenomella alba*, each with 16.7% frequency occurrence;

Epicoccum nigrum and *Fusarium trichothecioides* possessed least frequency occurrence (8.3%).

Figure 1: Representation of keratinophilic fungal genera recovered from: (A) Khardung soil and (B) Khardung La soil.

(A)

(B)

As shown in the pie chart (Fig 1A), the genera *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* recovered from Khardung soils were represented by 5 different species each, whereas the genera *Chrysosporium* and *Paecilomyces* were represented by 4 species and 3 species respectively. The genera *Acremonium*, *Penicillium* and *Gliocladium* were represented by 2 different species each whereas the genera *Beauveria*, *Cladosporium*, *Embellisia*, *Emericella*, *Epicoccum* and *Sagenomella* were represented by only 1 species each. The soils of Khardung La were represented maximally by *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* species each with 3 different species (Fig 1B), whereas only 1 species was recovered of *Beauveria*.

Scrutiny of available literature revealed that *Embellisiachlamydospora*, *Emericellavaricolor*, *Epicoccumnigrum*, *Fusariummoniliforme* var. *subglutinans* and *Sagenomella alba*, which were recovered in the present investigation from Khardung soils have not been reported earlier as keratinophilic and are therefore, new additions to this unique group of microorganisms.

Figure-2: Diversity indices of Khardung and Khardung La.

As depicted in figure 2, diversity indices show a significant difference in species richness between the two sites i.e., Khardung (29) and Khardung La (7). The value of Shannon's diversity index comes out to be 3.27 for Khardung and 1.88 for Khardung La, which shows that Khardung soils are more diverse and richer in species than Khardung La soils. The value of Simpson's diversity index comes out to be 0.96 for Khardung and 0.84 for Khardung La. As both these values are very near to 1, it points out towards more homogenous nature of the keratinophilic fungal species present in the soils of the two regions that were surveyed. Statistical analysis indicates that Khardung soils have greater system stability for the growth, development and diffusion of keratinophilic fungi than for Khardung La soils. According to Sorensen's similarity index, each of these sites showed a value of 38.89, which means that the species present in Khardung La soils are also prevalent in Khardung soils (Figure 1).

From these investigations, it is clear that higher altitudes (14,738 and 17,582 feet above sea level), cold temperature, violent winds and prevailing conditions of light do not prevent the

occurrence of keratinophilic fungal flora. However, their distribution is largely dependent on the existence of keratinous substrates of human and animal origin. These observations are in accordance with the findings of Mercantini *et al.*, [26, 27] who studied keratinophilic fungal flora of Antarctic soil.

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